

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF DIGITAL LEVELS OVER OPTIC LEVELS

Adambaev Alisher Ravshanbek ugli¹

Teacher of the Department of Geodesy, Cartography, Geography,
Urgench State University,

Bakhtiyorova Maftuna Maqsud qizi²

University student of Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre.

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the features, capabilities, advantages and disadvantages of levels developed in modern and traditional methods. The capabilities of the two generations of levels are given comparatively. The advantage of digital levels over optical levels is stated.

Currently, the highest level of automation of geometric levels is achieved when using digital levels. Their advantage over optical levels is that they are automatically counted from the rail, i.e. one of the biggest errors in levelling (human counting) has been eliminated. In digital levels, the calculation is automatically taken from the rails with a special barcode download, which is calculated after the process has been measured many times, and this calculation guarantees the accuracy of the measurement. The second important improvement in digital levels is electronic memory and software, real-time shooting. This allows you to straighten the shoulders of the station, which is very important, and at the same time get the results after the shooting. The results obtained can be processed in the software together with the data of other geodetic works, as it is equipped with memory cards or connectors (USB cable and port) for receiving data from digital levels to the computer. All digital levels are easy to install and have high accuracy, so levelling usually uses invar rails, fiberglass rails are used for less accurate work, because they have a high coefficient of thermal expansion, so their accuracy is lower. Barcode rails cannot be used for consideration [4].

Digital levels are usually used for high-precision geodetic works. Especially in the study of the deformation of structures and the movements of the crust, in the study of their natural causes and the causes which are caused by human factors. The main manufacturers of digital levels are the following companies: Trimble, Leica, Sokkia, Topcon. The main difference between digital and optical levels is in the accounting system. In digital levels, the metering device is an CCD matrix, which counts from a special rail and accurately calculates the height of the rails from zero to the level.

The advantages of working in this system

The human factor associated with getting value is zero. Often recordings are made in internal memory, which speeds up the process of measuring the area.

Compared to humans, electronics perform calculations more accurately.

Ability to perform optical measurements (if the battery is dead or for some reason it is not possible to take into account).

Installed programs to speed up work. Disadvantages.

The condition is to illuminate the rail in all directions. That the rail should be visible in its entirety.

Always keep in mind that certain conditions must be met to ensure the accuracy of the measurement:

The device must be configured.

The stand should be protected from vibrations during measurements.

Observe the rail level (for digital levels), the rail should be rotated (for optical measurements) to ensure accurate measurement results [5]. Digital levels differ from traditional levels in that they are equipped with electronics and are equipped with special work programs. This allows you to automate the process of field measurements and the development of results, including:

automatic counting on bar-coded level rails;

- automatic adjustments to the measurement results for the fact that the sight tube is not parallel to the axis of the visor and the axis of the cylinder, and for the conditions of curvature and refraction;
- automatic check of the results of measuring the leveling and relative height of the leveling shoulders;
- display the height of the points on the board;
- use a memory card to record measured data;
- Ease of operation of the device, as well as ease of use

With Dini 11 and Dini 21 digital levels, 1 km of road can be measured with an accuracy of 0.3 mm through the invar rail in the forward and reverse directions, and with an accuracy of 1 mm using a simple folding rail. Points at a distance of

m to 100 m from the station are measured in 4 seconds. The operating limit of the compensators installed in the levels is 151. The tool is mounted on a horizontal circle, the fractional value of which is 10. The software installed on the levels allows you to perform processes such as separate measurement, re-measurement, center and forward leveling, planning work and leveling the level path. The numbers taken from the rack can be saved in the memory of the levels or read from the instrument display (screen) and recorded in the log. In recent years, Dini digital levels have been produced by Trimble under the names Dini 12, Dini 12T and Dini 22 [1].

Digital Levels Type Trimble Religion 0.7	Digital Levels Type Trimble Religion 0.7
Accuracy (2 walks per 1 km) mm	
- barcode invar rake	0.7
- on a standard bar with a barcode	1.3
Vision tube approximation, krat	26
Minimum visibility distance, m	1.3
Image	directly
Compensator performance limit	15
Keyboard	It has 4 location keys consisting of 19-letter letters and numbers
Internal memory, data line	30,000 each
Display	Graphic, 240x160, monochrome, with lighting.
Water and dust protection	IP55
Operating temperature limit, ° S	-20 to +50 each
Power supply	Internal battery - lithium-ion, 7.4 B / 2.4 Ah
Performance time, p	30
Weight, kg	3.5

Like all levels, optical levels vary in accuracy. Accuracy depends directly on the compensation system - the more accurate the levels, the lower the error should be in the

compensator. In addition, the accuracy depends on the multiplicity of the optical system designed to receive the count from the rail. Thus, the accuracy of the high-precision level compensator NA2 / NAK2 is 0.3 mm, which allows the optical system to make an error of 0.3 mm by walking 2 times at a distance of 1 km with a 40-degree zoom. This accuracy is also ensured by the use of a special flat parallel plate with micrometer screws to obtain accurate counting. Because the survey is carried out not only on a single level, but also with accessories, so the tripod and rails used must also provide the necessary accuracy. It is also necessary to use a stationary wooden tripod, and an invar rail for high-precision calculations. They have small coefficients of thermal expansion, which allows for the highest accuracy. The most common level of this type, which has already become a classic device, is the level of this optical type [2].

The main advantage of optical levels is low cost, convenience and high accuracy. Disadvantages - Measurements can only be made in the presence of two people. In addition, optical levels are adjusted manually and require constant level control, calculations also need to be done manually, unlike optical levels, which can usually be used only by professionals with certain professional skills, laser levels are highly automated, for anyone makes it easy to use. This device is an invaluable aid in construction and repair work [3].

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of digital levels in all industries increases cocktail productivity, but this update can be applied more in well-off industries, as this work requires a good deal of money. In my opinion, working at digital levels is easy, convenient and has few errors, so I think it is necessary to apply digital levels to all areas.

Figure 2. Vega L30 optical levels

Type	Optical levels
Models	Vega L30
Zoom rate	30x
Accuracy	1.5 mm

Illuminated optics	Yes
Limb (grading limit)	360 ⁰
Minimum measuring pressure of the limb	1 ⁰
Minimum viewing distance	0.6 m
Maximum viewing distance	120 m

Lens diameter	40 mm
Limb pressure	In degrees
Compensator limit (leveling)	± 15'
The presence of fluid levels	Yes
Body material	Iron
Collection	Pin for adjustment, guide, threaded plumb line, a case for carrying.
Weight	1.5 kg

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